

Dynamic Service Provisioning in Multi-Band over Spatial Division Multiplexing Optical Networks

Ramon Casellas, Laia Nadal, Francisco J. Vilchez, Carlos Hernández-Chulde,
Josep Maria Fàbrega, Ricard Vilalta, Ricardo Martínez, Raul Muñoz
CTTC-CERCA, Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss n7, 08860 Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain

e-mail: ramon.casellas@cttc.es

Abstract—This paper summarizes the design and implementation of a Software Defined Networking control plane for Multi-Band WDM over Spatial Domain Multiplexing (SDM) networks, either in terms of bundles of fibers (BoF) or multicore fibers. We present the overall architecture and main challenges, the proposed protocol extensions and the implemented path computation and resource allocation algorithm. We illustrate the solution with a proof-of-concept using CTTC FlexOpt SDN controller, which includes an ongoing multi-band over SDM (MBoSDM) optical node prototype being developed in the context of the SEASON European Project.

Keywords—SDN control plane, Multiband optical networks, SDM, MBoSDM, Multilayer Optical Networks, Multi Granular Optical Nodes, Transport API, Data models.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increase of Internet traffic, driven by the expansion of cloud services, home broadband, video streaming, and artificial intelligence applications, requires additional network capacity. With moderate traffic projections, spectrum demand is expected to reach 50 THz by 2031 [1]. One short to mid-term solution is the adoption of Ultra-Wide Band (UWB)-Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) [2] systems, which utilize a broad wavelength range from 1260 nm to 1625 nm, spanning the O, E, S, C, and L bands.

At the long-term, solutions based on Spatial Domain Multiplexing (SDM) based on either bundles of fibers or multi-core fibers are required, and further capacity scaling means addressing the spatial dimension [3, 4].

When using SDM, in single level optical networks, parallel links are deployed either as bundles of fibers (BoF) or as multi-core fibers with fan-in / fan-out systems. To date, such SDM systems are mostly point-to-point and switching only happens at the media channel (DWDM) level and SDM or spatial layer is systematically terminated at each node and transported OTS_i signals are switched (their media channels, referred to as DWDM switching). Although systematically terminating spatial layer connections and switching at the DWDM layer has potentially the best efficiency in terms of blocking probability and network capacity -- given the fine granularity of switching at the upper layers -- in practice, this approach has multiple drawbacks when scaling to required capacity involving many fibers and/or spatial cores. For example, the required Wavelength Selective Switches (WSS) may become a bottleneck or simply unfeasible due to the number of required ports to ensure contention-less, color-less and contention-less nodes or not being able to cover the whole optical spectrum with the required granularity, which requires more complex node architectures introducing e.g. per-band filtering and dedicated planes [5].

On the other hand, multi-level networks (see Fig. 1) extend single level networks by introducing different switching granularities (levels), and these may encompass, for example, WDM switching (media channel switching, either in fixed-flexi-grid) and Fiber / Core switching in single nodes. Efficient path computation algorithms and control plane architectures are required to operate such networks.

Fig. 1. Multi-Stage optical networks showing DWDM and SDM switching and DWDM service grooming & bypassing

Fig. 2. SDN Controller GUI shows the concept of virtual link and aggregation. An SDM connection (red dash) uses a fiber core, and the connection supports a DWDM multi-band link (purple link) between the SDM connection endpoints

II. CONTROL PLANE DESIGN

A. Model Driven Control Plane

The increased programmability of optical devices, extended to support multi-band transmission and switching [6], is a driver for the adoption of Software Defined Networking (SDN) which, along with telemetry platforms, enable autonomous networks. Model driven development (MDD) is an approach to design distributed systems based on the systematic use of data models, used with optimized protocols so applications can be developed and, to enable dynamic service provisioning, the optical controller exports a standard northbound interface (NBI). The role of an SDN controller is then to enable the provisioning of connectivity services (in this case, media channels) using virtual links and aggregation (see Fig.2) where connections at the SDM layer become links at the WDM layer.

A. Overall Architecture

The control plane architecture relies on a single SDN controller that is responsible for the Optical Line System (OLS). This OLS controller exports a North Bound Interface that extends the transport application programming interface (TAPI, see Fig.3) to support the provision of media channels or SDM connections. Main entities such as Connectivity Service End-Points (CSEPs), Connection End Points (CEPs) and Node Edge Points (NEPs) have been augmented to convey information about the status of e.g. fibers or cores within a single traffic engineering link.

B. Path Computation Algorithm

The path computation function is a key function of the OLS controller. The objective is to find a path between two endpoints (Service Interface Points) and allocate a continuous media channel (frequency slot) in a multi-band context. For

Fig. 3. Graphical Representation showing the TAPI context and the modelling of the network showing the extensions to SDM related to core allocation, as exposed by the MBoSDM OLS SDN Controller

this, the function may decide to allocate lower layer connections (SDM connections) that become higher layer links. The complexity of such algorithms is high [7], and in this work, we have devised an algorithm that works as follows: upon the arrival of a connection, try to find a path in the DWDM layer, ensuring sufficient QoT based on predefined parameters such as reach. A given DWDM link has a pool of the C, L and S bands. If this path computation fails, the algorithm shall look for additional SDM connections – with or without core/fiber continuity constraints, based on hardware limitations and capabilities) and given the additional DWDM links they induce, try again the DWDM allocation. If the algorithm cannot find a WDM frequency slot and cannot create a SDM connection directly between the end nodes, the algorithm fails.

Fig. 4. High Level messages between the SDN controller and the SDN agent, based on the pre-defined operations

C. Control Plane Workflow

The operation of the SDN control plane starts with the onboarding of the controlled topology. In this work, we have considered different topologies with real or emulated hardware. For example, one of the topologies is based on the Telefonica topology with 65 nodes, and 270 links with 5 cores per MCF. The Operator Support System or Client may retrieve the TAPI context and available resources, including the

different nodes, links and their switching capabilities as well as available resources.

At some point, the user proceeds with media channel service provisioning S1 between nodes. Upon request, the path computation algorithm finds a path which may or may not involve the provisioning of SDM connections (with continuous core between endpoints in the case of core continuity constraint) and the subsequent instantiation of virtual link(s). Such DWDM links are managed in virtual network topology (VNT) and keep track of both the underlying supporting connections as well as the client services. Note that links induced by SDM connections can be reused by different DWDM services (grooming). When the service connections are released if a SDM connection is no longer used by a WDM connection, the supported DWDM link is removed and the SDM connection is released.

As part of the provisioning process, the OLS controller interacts with the SDN agents within the network elements to configure the optical nodes. Based on a high level abstraction there are different operations that can be done: ADD or DROP operations of a media channel between an add/Drop port and a degree port, cross-connect a given media channel given its frequency slot and input/output ports and, for the SDM layer ADD or DROP a client port of the SDM layer into the SDM fiber or cross-connect a core between an input and output core (see Fig.4). The next section details the SDN agent developed in our prototype.

Let us note (Fig.5) that when the data plane is emulated, the controller can be used to evaluate the performance of the system and the algorithm, by either using Markovian processes or evaluating the accepted traffic load (network capacity) to reach a blocking rate of e.g.1%. Fig 5 shows the network state retrieved via the RESTCONF/ TAPI interfaces after batch of service requests: 336 connectivity services:110 SDM core - supporting 110 virtual DWDM links (purple) and 226 flexi-grid services. Links show core allocation (SDM) and freq. slots (DWDM). Links are either physical (SDM links) or logical WDM links supported by a connection in the SDM layer.

Fig. 5. Network state after batch of service requests: 336 connectivity services:110 SDM core - supporting 110 virtual DWDM links (purple) and 226 flexi-grid services. Links show core allocation (SDM) and freq. slots (DWDM)

III. MBoSDM OPTICAL NODE PROTOTYPE

A MBoSDM node prototype is currently being developed at CTTC premises, to demonstrate transparent switching at the WDM and SDM level. As part of the ongoing work, the node must be controlled by the SDN control plane described in this work within the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed. For details on the components of the nodes, please refer to [8]. The next section describes the SDN agent that enables remote configuration and control of the MBoSDM node.

Fig. 5. MBoSDM node prototype being developed [8].

A. Control Plane Agent

An SDN control plane agent has been developed using the Netopeer framework. We have defined a Yang model that maps the previously mentioned high level functions into the creation of “connections” within the node. The SDN controller uses NETCONF to create or release connections and provide the required parameters. We can see a simplified Yang model for the SDN agent in which the main data node is the list of connections that can be modified by the SDN controller. The creation (or deletion) of a connection in the data plane triggers the process of hardware configuration using the low-level interfaces.

```

module: season-mbosdm-node
  +--rw node
    | +--rw address      inet:ip-address
    | +--rw node_id     yang:uuid
    | +--ro ports
    | | +--ro port* [id]
    | |   +--ro id      uint32
    | |   +--ro name?   string
    | |   +--ro direction? port-direction
    | |   +--ro type?   port-type
    | +--rw connections
    |   +--rw connection* [name]
    |     +--rw name      string
    |     +--rw input_port uint32
    |     +--rw output_port uint32
    |     +--rw input_core uint32
    |     +--rw output_core uint32
    |     +--rw band?     enumeration
  
```

```

|         +--rw n      int16
|         +--rw m      uint16
+--ro info
  +--ro software_version? string
  +--ro hardware_version? string
  
```

CONCLUSIONS

In the context of the work done in the European Project SEASON, this paper has presented a control plane for MBoSDM networks, showing the main challenges and design choices. We have demonstrated its applicability in MBoSDM nodes both at the control plane level with large topologies as well as the ongoing proof-of-concept being done in the ADRENALINE CTTC testbed.

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